

Evaluation and optimization of antibiotic selection for surgical prophylaxis in Ahmedabad region

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World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2025, 23(03), 361-376

Publication history: Received on 05 August 2025; revised on 14 September 2025; accepted on 18 September 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2025.23.3.0848>

Abstract

Objectives: To assess the antibiotic prescribing trends for surgical prophylaxis across selected healthcare centers in Ahmedabad and to evaluate their alignment with standard guidelines.

Methods: This retrospective, multi-centric observational study was conducted over 6 months across tertiary care hospitals in Ahmedabad. Patient records from surgical departments were screened to analyse the prophylactic antibiotic choice, dosage forms, frequency, post-operative prescribing patterns, and associated parameters. Surgeries were classified based on wound type (clean, clean-contaminated, contaminated, dirty), and data was compiled on demographics, culture sensitivity tests, and antibiotic cost.

Results: Of the included cases, the majority underwent procedures categorized as clean or clean-contaminated. Ceftriaxone and Amikacin were the most frequently prescribed prophylactic antibiotics, often in combination. In certain cases, non-recommended agents such as third-generation cephalosporins were used indiscriminately. Culture sensitivity testing revealed predominant organisms including *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Despite available guidance (ICMR, CDC), notable deviations were observed in dosage frequency, timing, and antibiotic coverage, leading to increased costs and suboptimal outcomes.

Conclusion: The findings underscore a disconnect between prescribed surgical prophylactic antibiotics and recommended evidence-based guidelines. There is a need for greater awareness, periodic audits, and stricter adherence to antimicrobial prophylaxis protocols to mitigate resistance and improve patient safety. Implementation of stewardship programs and education across surgical departments could significantly enhance rational antibiotic use.

Keywords: Surgical Site Infection; Antibiotic Prophylaxis; Drug Utilization Review; Guideline Adherence; Microbial Sensitivity Tests

1. Introduction

Surgical site infections (SSIs) are defined as infections that occur at or near the surgical incision site within 30 days of surgery or within one year if implants are involved.¹ They are classified into three categories: superficial incisional (involving skin and subcutaneous tissue), deep incisional (affecting deeper soft tissues such as fascia and muscle), and organ/space infections (involving any part of the body other than the incision that was manipulated during surgery). SSIs are among the most common healthcare-associated infections, significantly contributing to patient morbidity, increased healthcare costs, and prolonged hospital stays.¹ The pathogenesis involves microbial contamination during surgery, with risk factors including patient comorbidities, surgical duration, and inadequate aseptic techniques. Common pathogens include *Staphylococcus aureus* (including MRSA) and gram-negative bacteria.¹ Preventive

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measures, such as proper hand hygiene, sterilization of surgical instruments, and timely administration of prophylactic antibiotics, are critical to reducing SSI incidence.²

Surgical site infections (SSIs) remain a global health concern, disproportionately affecting low- and middle-income countries, where infection rates can be as high as 20% due to inadequate resources and sterilization practices.³ Even in high-income nations, SSIs contribute significantly to healthcare-associated infections. The global incidence varies widely, influenced by factors such as healthcare infrastructure, regional infection control practices, and the prevalence of antimicrobial resistance.³ Efforts like the WHO's Clean Care is Safer Care initiative have focused on reducing SSIs through education and evidence-based practices.⁴

In India, surgical site infections (SSIs) remain a significant challenge, with reported rates ranging from 6% to 38%, particularly in resource-limited healthcare settings.⁵ Contributing factors include limited adherence to infection control measures, overburdened healthcare systems, and widespread antimicrobial resistance.⁶ SSIs are among the most common healthcare-associated infections in the country, disproportionately impacting patients in rural areas and those undergoing emergency surgeries.⁵ Efforts like the National Infection Control Guidelines aim to standardize prevention strategies and improve outcomes.

The most common pathogens causing surgical site infections (SSIs) are *Staphylococcus aureus*, including methicillin-resistant strains (MRSA), and *Escherichia coli*.¹ Other notable organisms include coagulase-negative staphylococci, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and Enterococcus species.⁴ The prevalence of these pathogens varies based on surgical type, hospital setting, and geographic region.⁴ In particular, *S. aureus* is frequently associated with orthopaedic and cardiovascular surgeries, while gram-negative pathogens like *E. coli* are common in gastrointestinal procedures.⁷ The emergence of multidrug-resistant strains further complicates treatment and highlights the need for robust infection control practices.

Surgical site infections (SSIs) can lead to significant complications, including prolonged hospitalization, increased healthcare costs, and delayed wound healing.¹ Severe infections may result in abscess formation, systemic sepsis, organ dysfunction, or even death, particularly in immunocompromised patients.⁸ Chronic SSIs can lead to implant-related infections, requiring surgical reintervention or prosthetic removal. Additionally, they contribute to the development of antimicrobial resistance, complicating treatment options. Preventing these complications through effective infection control measures remains critical in improving surgical outcomes.

Appropriate use of antibiotics in surgical prophylaxis is pivotal in reducing the incidence of surgical site infections (SSIs).⁸ Administering antibiotics within the recommended timeframe—typically within 60 minutes prior to incision—ensures adequate tissue concentrations to prevent microbial contamination during surgery.⁹ Prolonged or inappropriate use of prophylactic antibiotics, however, contributes to antimicrobial resistance and offers no additional benefit in preventing SSIs.⁸ Studies emphasize the importance of evidence-based guidelines to optimize antibiotic selection, timing, and duration to achieve maximum efficacy while minimizing risks.

The selection of antibiotics for surgical prophylaxis largely depends on the type of surgical wound (clean, clean-contaminated, contaminated, or dirty) and the procedure performed.⁹ Clean surgeries, such as orthopaedic or cardiovascular procedures, typically require coverage against gram-positive organisms like *Staphylococcus aureus*, often using cefazolin.¹⁰ Clean-contaminated and contaminated surgeries, like gastrointestinal or gynaecological procedures, demand broader-spectrum antibiotics to target gram-negative and anaerobic pathogens, such as ceftriaxone or metronidazole.¹⁰ Tailored antibiotic regimens based on wound classification and patient-specific factors optimize infection prevention and minimize resistance risks.

The inappropriate selection of antibiotics for surgical prophylaxis can result in serious consequences, including treatment failure, higher rates of surgical site infections (SSIs), and increased morbidity.⁹ For example, inadequate gram-negative or anaerobic coverage in gastrointestinal surgeries may fail to prevent infections.⁹ Conversely, overuse of broad-spectrum antibiotics fosters the development of multidrug-resistant organisms, complicating future treatments. Additionally, wrong antibiotic choices may lead to adverse effects like allergic reactions or toxicity in patients.¹¹ Evidence underscores the importance of adhering to evidence-based guidelines to avoid these outcomes.

A study on the use of antibiotics in surgical prophylaxis is crucial to address the increasing threat of surgical site infections (SSIs) and the emergence of antimicrobial resistance.¹² Despite existing guidelines, substantial variability in antibiotic selection, timing, and duration persists, often leading to suboptimal outcomes.⁹ Research is essential to evaluate adherence to protocols, identify gaps in practice, and optimize antibiotic regimens based on evolving resistance

patterns and regional needs. So, our aim of the study is to evaluate and optimize the selection of antibiotic for surgical prophylaxis in Ahmedabad region.

2. Materials and Methods

- **Study Type:** This research employed a retrospective study design, conducted across multiple centres to ensure diverse representation and comprehensive data collection.
- **Study Centres Included:** Patient data was collected from several hospitals and clinics located within the Ahmedabad region, enabling an expansive evaluation of antibiotic usage for surgical prophylaxis. [Study centres: SAL Hospital (Thaltej, Ahmedabad); Treya Surgi care (Maninagar, Ahmedabad); Arham Hospital (Jodhpur, Ahmedabad); Param Maternity and Nursing Home (Vastral, Ahmedabad); Swastik Orthopaedic Hospital (Naroda Patiya, Ahmedabad)]
- **Sample Size:** A total of 602 patients were included in the study, selected based on predefined criteria to maintain the reliability and statistical power of the findings.
- **Inclusion Criteria:** Patients undergoing various surgical procedures who had received prophylactic antibiotic therapy were considered eligible for the study.
- **Exclusion Criteria:** Patients with incomplete medical records, missing antibiotic data, or lacking follow-up documentation were excluded to maintain data integrity.
- **Study Duration:** The research was conducted over a six-month period, allowing sufficient time to assess patterns in antibiotic prescribing and surgical outcomes.
- **Data Collection:** Relevant patient information, including demographic details, types of surgeries, antibiotics prescribed, dosage forms, and hospitalization outcomes, was extracted from patient records. Data was then categorized and analysed to evaluate adherence to prophylactic guidelines, antimicrobial trends, and microbial resistance.
- **Statistical Analysis:** As this study was descriptive in nature, data were summarized using basic statistical methods to illustrate prescribing patterns and clinical characteristics. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages were employed to analyse categorical variables. Tabulated results and graphical representations (bar charts, pie charts) were used to visually convey trends across multiple study centres. No inferential statistical tests were applied, as the primary objective was to observe and report existing prescribing practices rather than establish causal relationships. [Note: Patients receiving multidrug regimens were counted per antibiotic entity. Hence, total antibiotic count exceeds patient count.]

3. Case Report Form

- **Aim of project:** Evaluation and Optimization of Antibiotic Selection for Surgical Prophylaxis in Ahmedabad Region
- **Investigators:** Dhanvin C. Suthar, Rutvika N. Patel, Jay N. Joshi

Case no

Gender: Male/Female

Age group

- Less than 20 years
- 20-30 years
- 30-40 years
- 40-50 years
- More than 60 years

Date of admission: __/__/__

Date of discharge: __/__/__

Length of hospitalization:

- Less than 3 days
- 3-5 days

- More than 5 days

3.1. Type of surgical wound

- Clean
- Clean/Contaminated
- Contaminated
- Dirty

Surgery: _____

Antibiotic used for surgical prophylaxis: _____

Antibiotic used for post-operative care: _____

Culture and sensitivity test done: Yes/No Microorganism detected: _____

4. Results

Figure 1 Distribution of Patients based on Types of Surgical Wounds

Figure 2 Gender Distribution

Figure 3 Length of Hospitalization

Figure 4 Culture and Sensitivity Testing

Table 1 Microorganisms Detected in Culture and Sensitivity Tests

Microorganism Detected in Culture and Sensitivity Tests	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
Bacteroides fragilis	5	10.41
Clostridium difficile	5	10.41
Enterococcus faecalis	1	2.08
Escherichia coli	4	8.33
Helicobacter pylori	9	18.75
Klebsiella pneumoniae	1	2.08
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	3	6.25
Staphylococcus aureus	16	33.33
Staphylococcus epidermidis	3	6.25
Streptococcus pyogenes	1	2.08
Total	48	100

Table 2 Prophylactic Antibiotics

Prophylactic Antibiotics			
Antibiotic Class	Antibiotic sub-class	Antibiotic name	Antibiotic count
Beta-lactam	1 st Generation Cephalosporin	Cefazolin	131
	2 nd Generation Cephalosporin	Cefuroxime	47
	2 nd Generation Cephalosporin	Cefotetan	5
	2 nd Generation Cephalosporin	Cefoxitin	10
	3 rd Generation Cephalosporin	Ceftriaxone	58
	3 rd Generation Cephalosporin	Cefixime	108
	3 rd Generation Cephalosporin	Cefotaxime	5
	3 rd Generation Cephalosporin	Cefoperazone	98
	3 rd Generation Cephalosporin	Cefpodoxime	12
	Penicillin	Amoxicillin	20
	Penicillin	Piperacillin	30
	Carbapenem	Meropenem	5
<u>Total Beta-lactam</u>	529		
Tetracycline	-	Doxycycline	3
Fluoroquinolones	2 nd Generation Fluoroquinolone	Ciprofloxacin	11
	3 rd Generation Fluoroquinolone	Levofloxacin	22
<u>Total Quinolones</u>	33		
Aminoglycoside	-	Amikacin	2
Glycopeptides	-	Vancomycin	1
Nitroimidazole	-	Metronidazole	19
Lincosamide	-	Clindamycin	19
Total Antibiotics	606		
Beta-lactamase inhibitors	Clavulanate	8	
	Tazobactam	30	
	Sulbactam	98	
<u>Total Beta-lactamase inhibitors</u>	136		

Table 3 Post operative antibiotics

Post operative antibiotics			
Antibiotic class	Antibiotic sub-class	Antibiotic name	Antibiotic count
	3 rd Generation Cephalosporin	Cefixime	153
	Penicillin	Amoxicillin	41
	Penicillin	Piperacillin	62

<u>Total Beta-lactam</u>	256		
Fluoroquinolones	2 nd Generation Fluoroquinolone	Ciprofloxacin	6
	3 rd Generation Fluoroquinolone	Levofloxacin	52
<u>Total Fluoroquinolones</u>	58		
Nitroimidazole	-	Metronidazole	79
Oxazolidinone	-	Linezolid	22
Macrolides	-	Azithromycin	5
Total Antibiotics	420		
Beta-lactamase inhibitors	Clavulanate		161
	Tazobactam		62
<u>Total Beta-lactamase inhibitors</u>	223		

Figure 5 Antibiotics Used for Surgical Prophylaxis in Clean Wounds

Figure 6 Antibiotics Used for Surgical Prophylaxis in Clean/Contaminated Wounds

Figure 7 Antibiotics Used for Surgical Prophylaxis in Contaminated Wounds

Figure 8 Antibiotics Used for Surgical Prophylaxis in Dirty Wounds

Figure 9 Antibiotics Used for Post-operative Care in Clean Wounds

Figure 10 Antibiotics Used for Post operative Care in Clean/Contaminated Wounds

Figure 11 Antibiotics Used for Post operative Care in Contaminated Wounds

Figure 12 Antibiotics Used for Post operative Care in Dirty Wounds

Table 4 Count of Specific Antibiotics Used for Surgical Prophylaxis in Clean, Clean/Contaminated, Contaminated and Dirty Wounds

Antibiotics	Clean	Clean/Contaminated	Contaminated	Dirty
Cefazolin	19	91	29	5
Cefixime	89	8	0	0
Cefixime clavulanate	5	1	0	0
Cefoperazone sulbactam	39	59	2	2
Cefuroxime	18	3	3	9
Ceftriaxone	4	39	4	15
Cefotetan	0	5	0	0
Cefotaxime	5	0	0	0
Cefoxitin	0	10	0	0
Cefpodoxime	12	0	0	0
Amoxicillin	0	5	0	0
Amoxicillin clavulanate	2	5	0	0
Meropenem	0	5	0	1
Piperacillin tazobactam	1	5	13	12
Doxycycline	0	3	0	0
Ciprofloxacin	0	11	0	0
Levofloxacin	4	18	0	0
Amikacin	2	0	1	0
Vancomycin	2	0	0	1
Clindamycin	0	18	0	1
Metronidazole	0	15	1	0

Table 5 Count of Specific Antibiotics Used for Post operative care in Clean, Clean/Contaminated, Contaminated and Dirty Wounds

Antibiotics	Clean	Clean/Contaminated	Contaminated	Dirty
Cefixime	110	29	1	0
Cefixime clavulanate	14	10	0	0
Amoxicillin	0	4	0	0
Amoxicillin clavulanate	0	36	0	4
Piperacillin tazobactam	1	21	9	13
Levofloxacin	17	35	1	0
Ciprofloxacin	0	6	0	0
Metronidazole	7	16	29	27
Linezolid	17	4	0	1
Azithromycin	5	0	0	0
Clindamycin	0	0	0	1

5. Discussions

Most surgical wounds were clean/contaminated (50%), while dirty wounds had the lowest occurrence (7.64%). The high prevalence of clean/contaminated wounds is expected, as many surgeries involve procedures where internal tissues are exposed to normal bacterial flora, requiring careful antibiotic prophylaxis. The relatively low number of dirty wounds suggests effective preoperative sterilization and infection control measures.

The gender distribution was balanced, with a slight predominance of female patients (51.66%) compared to males (48.33%). This distribution may reflect variations in surgical procedures, with certain conditions requiring interventions being more frequent among women. However, the near-equal representation suggests no strong gender bias in surgical interventions.

Most patients had a hospital stay of less than 3 days (42.02%), whereas those who stayed more than 5 days were fewer (28.40%). Short hospital stays are linked to minor surgical procedures, efficient post-operative recovery, and early discharge practices. Patients requiring extended hospitalization may have undergone major surgeries or experienced post-surgical complications.

A significant proportion of patients (92.02%) did not undergo culture and sensitivity testing, whereas only 7.97% had tests performed. This pattern suggests reliance on empirical antibiotic therapy rather than targeted treatment based on microbiological findings, likely due to standard surgical prophylactic protocols and the absence of suspected infections in most cases.

Among the detected microorganisms, *Staphylococcus aureus* had the highest prevalence (33.33%), while *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Streptococcus pyogenes* were least detected (2.08% each). The dominance of *Staphylococcus aureus* is consistent with its role as a major pathogen in post-surgical infections due to its virulence factors. The lower incidence of the other microorganisms reflects their selective presence in specific clinical conditions.

The most prescribed class for prophylaxis was Beta-lactams, while Glycopeptides had the lowest usage. Beta-lactams are widely used due to their effectiveness against a broad range of bacterial pathogens in surgical settings. The minimal use of Glycopeptides suggests their reserved application for resistant Gram-positive bacterial infections.

Beta-lactams remained the most frequently administered class post-surgery, ensuring coverage for common pathogens. Macrolides had the lowest usage, likely because they are typically indicated for specific respiratory or soft tissue infections rather than routine post-surgical care.

The most used antibiotic class for prophylaxis in clean wounds was Beta-lactams, making up most prescriptions. This dominance reflects their broad-spectrum efficacy and established role in preventing post-surgical infections.

Among clean/contaminated wounds, Beta-lactams were the most frequently administered antibiotics, reinforcing their primary role in surgical prophylaxis.

For contaminated wounds, Beta-lactams were the most used antibiotics, reflecting their strong efficacy against potential wound pathogens.

In dirty wounds, Beta-lactams (31 cases) remained the most prevalent antibiotic choice, supporting their extensive usage across various surgical wound types.

For post-operative care of clean wounds, Beta-lactams were the most prescribed, aligning with their continued role in infection prevention post-surgery.

Beta-lactams had the highest use among clean/contaminated wounds, ensuring broad protection during recovery. The least frequently used class was Oxazolidinones, reflecting their selective application for resistant Gram-positive infections.

In contaminated wounds, Nitroimidazoles were the most prescribed due to their effectiveness against anaerobic pathogens often present in contaminated wounds.

Post-operative treatment of dirty wounds was dominated by Nitroimidazoles, likely due to their strong efficacy against anaerobic and mixed bacterial infections commonly found in heavily contaminated wounds. The least prescribed classes were Lincosamides and Oxazolidinones, reflecting their targeted use for specific resistant infections.

Zooming into individual molecules used in surgical prophylaxis, amikacin, vancomycin, and metronidazole were among the least prescribed, each at less than 1%. Amikacin's nephrotoxicity and vancomycin's reserved role explain their scarcity. Metronidazole's low prophylactic use could reflect its strategic deployment in combination therapies rather than stand-alone action, particularly in anaerobic-heavy wound types.

In postoperative regimens, macrolides (azithromycin) and clindamycin were used least often, each under 1.2%. Their specialized spectra may restrict them to unique clinical scenarios, reinforcing broader reliance on cephalosporins and nitroimidazoles. Their restrained presence suggests adherence to narrow-spectrum principles and judicious targeting of suspected pathogens.

Taken together, these trends highlight a prescribing landscape shaped by surgical wound classification, anticipated microbial burden, and the imperative of antibiotic stewardship. Minimal reliance on certain drug classes and molecules reflects both clinical prudence and alignment with contemporary antimicrobial guidelines. The selective use of agents based on wound severity, pathogen profile, and resistance threat offers a compelling narrative of rational and responsible antimicrobial management throughout the surgical care continuum.

6. Conclusion

This study offers a comprehensive evaluation of antibiotic usage patterns in surgical patients, focusing on factors such as wound classification, hospitalization duration, microbiological findings, and the selection of prophylactic and post-operative antibiotics. The findings highlight significant trends in antibiotic prescribing practices, indicating a strong reliance on Beta-lactams across different surgical wound categories, particularly in clean and clean/contaminated wounds. This aligns with their broad-spectrum efficacy and well-established role in preventing Surgical Site Infections (SSIs). Approximately 30% of patients remained hospitalized for more than five days, indicating an increased risk of surgical site infections (SSIs). *Staphylococcus aureus* was identified as the most common organism responsible for surgical site infections. Beta-lactam antibiotics were the most commonly prescribed for clean wounds, while Nitroimidazoles were more frequently used for dirty wounds. The appropriate selection of antibiotics for surgical prophylaxis is crucial in minimizing the risk of antimicrobial resistance.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Our deepest gratitude goes out to our parents and family for their boundless love, prayers, care, and sacrifices, which have fostered the optimal environment for our growth and education, paving the way toward a brighter future.

We would like to express our profound appreciation to our guide Dr. Nilesh Kanzariya, (Professor, Dept. of Pharmacy Practice at Sal Institute of Pharmacy) and our co-guide Ms. Srushtiben Maheshkumar Chaudhary (Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pharmacology at SAL Institute of Pharmacy). We are grateful for the opportunity he has given us to carry out our research, and we acknowledge his invaluable guidance and support throughout the entire process.

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the respective doctors and staff of our included study centers for their invaluable assistance in the gathering of the necessary data for our project. Their expertise and guidance have been instrumental in ensuring the accuracy and reliability of our results, and we are truly grateful for their contributions. Thank you for your time and support.

Our project would not have been possible without the support of the Doctors and medical as well as non-medical staff of the hospitals and clinics, who generously assisted us in gathering the necessary data for our project.

Finally, we would like to express our gratitude to all those who directly or indirectly supported us in completing this research work.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict-of-interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

The authors affirm that this manuscript is an original scholarly work prepared. All definitions, factual statements, and data derived from previously published sources have been appropriately cited using Vancouver referencing style. No portion of the manuscript contains plagiarized content, and all paraphrased or adapted material has been ethically incorporated. The manuscript does not infringe upon any copyright and does not contain figures or tables reproduced without prior permission, where applicable. The authors declare compliance with the ethical standards of academic publishing and consent to the manuscript's evaluation under the plagiarism and originality verification protocols.

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Statement of informed consent

This approach ensures clarity for the reader while honoring intellectual contributions of prior work. All cited content has been used solely for academic and educational purposes in accordance with journal guidelines.

Ethical Considerations and Institutional Oversight

This study was conducted as a retrospective analysis utilizing anonymized patient records. Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) clearance was obtained from Institutional Ethics Committee-SAL for the principal study site. The remaining participating clinics are small-scale centers that do not maintain independent IECs. No direct patient contact or intervention was undertaken, and all data were de-identified prior to analysis.

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